

Impact of Student- Teacher Relationship on Post- Primary Schools' administrative Effectiveness in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract- The study was conducted on impact of students' teacher relationship on post-primary schools' administrative effectiveness in Ondo State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised, teachers and students at secondary schools. The sample size of the study was One hundred and thirty (130) respondents were selected, through a simple sampling technique . Three research questions were raised. Data were collected through, a self-structured questionnaire by the researcher, titled, "Questionnaire on Impact of Student- Teacher Relationship on Post- Primary Schools' Administrative Effectiveness in Ondo State, Nigeria", fashioned on four likert rating scale; Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD), rated on 4,3,2, and 1 points). The research instruments were validated by three experts in Measurement and Evaluation .Its reliability was determined, through test-retest method at two weeks interval, 0.69 coefficient reliability was established. Data collected were analyzed, using descriptive statistics (frequency counts and simple percentage. Based on the results of the study, conclusions were made that student-teacher relationship could result into effective students' academic planning, achievement of school goals, improved students' academic performance, positive schools' climate, students' adherence to rule and regulation of the school and social-peace stability in the school. Therefore, recommendations were made that; teachers should establish a good relationship with their students; school managers should be educated on how to promote positive student-teacher relationship; students and teachers alike should be educated and enlightened on the benefits of students-teacher relationship to effective administration , and so on.

Keywords- Impact, Student- teacher, Relationship, Post- primary, Administrative, Effectiveness.

I. Introduction

Background to the Study

The development of any society depends on the quality of education, and the quality of education depends on the quality of teachers, students and effective involvement of parents in education (Clinton and Hattie (2013). Oyekan (2004), states that schools performance is a function of many factors which student-teacher relationship is on one .Teaching requires new teaching technique, teacher' good and professional conduct with the learners (Battin-Pearson 2000). Teachers play a vital position in promoting education, learning and professional growth of learners. It is believed that, academic success of learners and schools is due to strong teacher-student relationship. Some of authors have shown the truth that the quality connection between educators and learning are key elements to learning and good schools' administration. Student- teacher relationship could either be negative or positive (Zichner,2011).

Aultman, Williams-Jonson and Schutz, (2009) describes that the kind and worth of relationships formed by instructors and learners are key to successful teaching and learning. Through Aultman, Williams-Jonson, and Schutz, (2009) we learn that, a teacher has skills, attitude and knowledge which can play a significant role in students' academic performance and how to make a meaningful life after school. Students who have close, supportive and positive relationships with their teachers attain higher level of achievements than those students with more conflicting relationships with teachers. Dianat and Abedini (2016) describes that – to make a successful and effective learning happen, teachers need to be motivated, enthusiastic and engage students professionally.

In Nigeria, many researches are ongoing and many had already been done in the field of education to assess the effect of student-teacher relationship on school and academic performance, the scholars have witnessed that the lack of professional relationship between teachers and students have always been a challenge that has affected the sector of education in many negative ways. However, there is a well-built perception that the quality of teacher–student relationships is essential for learning and teaching in the learning contexts. Santrock (2007) asserts that relationship behaviours of instructors greatly influence academic performance. Santrock further describes that, instructors – student relationships are essential to one's social and emotional maturity, they have the potential influence on how a student succeeds in school. This is to say that, interpersonal teacher-student relationships develop student experiences with success by giving continual monitoring as the students move into the academic pursuit in schools. Oyekan (2004), suggests that at pre and post –primary levels of education learners need supports of their teachers because of their ages. Teachers must be engaging learners professionally, this will assist the learners emotionally, morally and academically. Further, teachers' roles are intricatives (knowledge dispenser, character builder ,modifier, guidance, counselor director, planner ,motivator , and so on).

Downey (2008) in his work says that, the quality of the relationship amongst a student and the teacher will results in a better degree of learning in the classroom. Through the student–teacher interaction, our conceptualizations to motivation lead to quality learning (Downey, 2008). (Downey, 2008) concludes that the interpersonal relationship among students and teachers in the instructional settings affect the school and students learning. Nugent (2009), suggests that creating a sense of wellbeing in the relationship between students and teachers influences learning and academic performance. Adeyinka and Adedotun (2013), state that teachers can motivate students during learning process. These relationships help a teacher to know the students' need and help them to feel protected and confident in learning development.

Larson (2011) says, nowadays, the existence of positive relationships inside the classroom is considered as possibly the most prominent factors in language learning, it may influence whichever in positive or negative ways, students' achievement and enthusiasm to work as well as advance their knowledge and social skills. O'Connor (2008), Newberry and Davis (2008) describe that teacher–student relationships are often mentioned as one of the core reasons for staying in the profession and they are a catalyst to learning, motivation and academic success. Downey (2008), Nugent (2009) and Larson (2011) state that from available literature, it seems that the formation of personal, supportive teacher - student relationships inherently demands emotional

involvements from teachers. For students, it is evident that the effective quality of the teacher – student relationship is a vital factor in their school and academic success.

Larson (2011), notes that nowadays the existence of positive relationships inside the classroom is considered as possibly the most prominent factors in performance of students, achievement and enthusiasm to work as well as advance their knowledge and social skills. In relation to that, most of the researches , specifically have carried out studies on factors that contribute to the massive failure of students within public secondary schools, and assessing learning materials and the environment than looking at how teacher –students’ relationship can affect the academic performance of the learners. The researchers observed that much have not been done on impact of student-teacher relationship on post primary schools’ administrative effectiveness thus, necessitated this study.

Statement of the Problem

In recent time in most of the nations of the world, academic performance is swindling due to poor schools’ administration. This has been attributed to a lot of factors. The unsavory situation remains a source of worry to academics , and they had conducted several studies on the menace issue to meaningfully halt the challenge .However, much have not been done on teacher-students relationship effective schools’ administration .It was this observed gap that motivated the researcher to carry out the study.

Purpose of the Study

The broad purpose of the study was to determine impact of student- teacher relationship on post-primary schools’ administrative effectiveness in Ondo State, Nigeria. The specific purposes were to :

1. Ascertain effects of student-relationship on students’ academic planning ; and
2. determine the effect of missing student –teachers’ relationship on achieving school’ goals.

Research Questions

Two research questions were raised to guide the conduct of the study.

1. Does student-teacher relationship have positive effects on students’ academic planning?
2. Will students who missed out on student-teacher relationship constitute as challenge to achieving schools’ goals?

II. Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. These allowed for an extensive harnessing of information on the study .The population of the study comprised, teachers and students at secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. A simple sampling technique was used to select One hundred and thirty (130) respondents for the study. Two research questions were raised .The respondents were six (6) schools’ Principals, fifty seven (57) teachers, sixty six (66) students, and one (1) Area Educational Officer (AEO).

A self-developed research instruments by the researcher, titled, ‘Impact of Student-Teacher Relationship on Post- Primary Schools Administrative Effectiveness in Ondo State, Nigeria’, fashioned on four likert rating scale; Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) , rated, and 4, 3, 2 and 1 points. The validity of the research instruments was done by three experts in Measurement and Evaluation. Its reliability was determined, through test-retest method at two weeks interval, and 0.69 coefficient reliability was established. Data generated on the research questions were analyzed, using descriptive statistics (frequency counts and simple percentages).

III. Presentation of Findings and Discussion of Results

Presentation of Findings

Research Question One: Does student-teacher relationships have positive effect on students’ academic planning?

Table 1: Showing frequency counts and simple percentage on does student-teacher relationships have positive effects on students’ academic planning.

	Students		Teachers	
	Variables	Percentage	Variables	Percentage
Helps students feel a strong connection to the teachers	-	-	50	87.7
It help students to feel cared for by their teachers in the learning contexts.	-	-	48	84.2
It builds trust and responsibility among teachers and students from day one of being in schools	36	54.5	-	-
It help students to have freedom of expression in the classroom	-	-	54	94.7
It causes students to feel ownerships in the classroom	30	45.4	-	-
It allow teachers and students to be an integral part of the classroom as they participate actively	46	69.9	-	-

Table 1 above, reveals that 87.7% of the respondents agree that teacher –student’s relationships help students feel a strong connection to the teacher in the classroom, 84.2% indicate that student- teacher’ relationships help students to feel cared about by

their teachers in the learning contexts, 94.7% say that student- teacher’ relationships help students to feel ownership in the classroom. Interestingly, 54.5% indicate that student- teacher relationships build trust and responsibility among teachers and students from day one of being in the school environment, 45.4% indicate that the student-teacher relationships make students feel ownership in the classroom, while 69.9% indicate that students-teacher relationships allow teacher and students to be an integral part of the classroom. This conforms with Myers and Pianta (2008) who say that students-teacher relationships are fundamental to healthy development of students in school especially to the students’ self-esteem. Therefore, it is concluded that majority of participants both teachers and students know that the components of students-teacher relationships are key elements of school in ensuring effective student academic planning.

Research Question Two: Does students who missed student-teacher relationship constitute as challenge to achieving school goals?

Table 2: Showing frequency counts and simple percentage on does students who missed out on student-teacher relationship constitute as challenge to achieving school goals

Challenges	Students		Teachers	
	Frequencies	Percentages	Frequencies	Percentages
Poor performance	64	96.9	55	96.4
School dropout	60	90.9	46	80.7
Immoral behaviour	40	60.6	50	87.7
Loneliness	56	84.8	54	94.7
Stress	30	45.4	42	73.6
Lack of confidence and lack of professional support	46	69.9	57	100

In this study which involved teachers, students, school heads and the Area Education Officer, 96.6% of the students and 96.4% of the teachers point out that poor performance is one of the biggest challenges that students who missed out on teacher – students’ relationships in the learning context are facing, while 90.9% of students and 80.7% of teachers maintain that school dropout is a challenge that students who missed out on teacher – students’ relationships in schools are facing. In the same vein, 60.6% of students as well as 87.7% of teachers have shown that one of the challenges is immoral behaviour due to the influence of peer pressures.

Loneliness is another challenge that was mentioned by 84.8% of student and 94.7% of teachers; 45.4% of students and 73.6% of teachers strongly maintain that students who missed out on teacher – student’s relationships experience stress in their life and as a result they lack professionals (contacts) that can influence their academic development.

Lack of confidence and professional support from the teachers is a challenge that students who missed supportive relationships with their teachers are facing. In this study, while 69.6% of students and 100% of teachers mentioned lack of confidence and lack of professional support as a major challenge concern, only 2 students did not mention any of the challenges.

To support these ideas Buyse et al. (2009) argue that children who experience conflicts in student-teacher relationships in the first grade demonstrate lower achievement, which is a major challenge to school goals attainment.

IV. Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, conclusions were made that student-teacher relationship could result into effective students' academic planning and achievement of school goals,

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Teachers should establish a good relationship with their students.
2. School managers should be educated on how to promote positive student-teacher relationship
3. Students and teachers alike should be educated and enlightened on the benefits of students-teacher relationship to effective primary schools' administration
4. Teacher Education Programme curriculum should be restructured to accommodate teacher-student relationship as a course.
5. Teachers should be well trained on strategies to foster positive and healthy interaction with their students , and so on.

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